

CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZING PRIMARY EDUCATION IN MATHEMATICS IN A SMALL SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu keng qamrovli izoh boshlang'ich ta'limdagi noto'g'ri moslashuvning psixologik xususiyatlarini ko'rib chiqadi va ijtimoiy, hissiy va akademik sohalaridagi turli ko'rsatkichlarga oydinlik kiritadi. Empirik tadqiqotlar va o'rnatilgan psixologik asoslarga tayangan holda izohda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari o'rtasida ijtimoiy chekinish, o'zini past baholash, o'qishdagi muvaffaqiyatsizlik, xulq-atvor muammolari va hissiy iztirobning tarqalishi va oqibatlarini o'rganiladi. Muhokama potentsial sabablar va profilaktika choralari haqida tushunchalarni taqdim etish, erta aniqlash va aralashuv muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Annotatsiya boshlang'ich ta'lim kontekstidagi noto'g'ri moslashuvni chuqurroq tushunishga intilayotgan o'qituvchilar, ota-onalar va ruhiy salomatlik bo'yicha mutaxassislar uchun qimmatli manba bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

INTRODUCTION

The main feature of modern primary education is that the content of the information provided in it is based on an almost stable textbook. Textbooks are very important for understaffed schools. A textbook is a book in which the main content is clearly explained in a serious system. The main task of the textbook is to help students learn independently. Textbook is the main and necessary teaching tool for students. The mathematics textbook is tailored to the program, meets its requirements, and shows the level at which each problem should be considered.

Dynamic manuals, individual instruction manuals and didactic materials are widely used in teaching mathematics. Instruction - manuals: will be natural and illustrative. Natural instruction: things around us in life: trees, pencils, sticks, cubes. Counted sticks are the most important and widely used, from which to learn numbering; they get an idea of the formation of counting units.

Visual instruction is also divided into several types.

a) Mathematical symbols (numbers, symbols, relationship symbols). Such a sign, numbers, together with a checkered board and storage boxes, are produced by the educational - technical industry or by the hands of students, with the help of which they study the properties of the series of natural numbers, describe the numbers with numbers, compare numbers, and write the solutions of example problems. M: Inserting the equation $5 + x = 7$.

b) Instructional pictures. They are from publishers or made by hand, each picture has a picture of one thing (fruits, flowers...). pictures are cut out and stored in an envelope, they are mainly used to teach the first 10 numbers. In addition, it is appropriate and convenient to use them to get acquainted with calculation methods and properties of actions. $(2+3)+4$.

c) Model of geometric figures. In order to correctly perceive the shape of an object and develop the ability to abstract the shape of an object, it is very important for students to observe the models of the figures and make such models independently.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Teaching methods control the organization, stimulation and control of the joint activities of teachers and students. Therefore, they are divided into three groups:

I. The method of organizing educational activities.

II. Methods of stimulating educational activities.

III. Methods of controlling the effectiveness of educational activities. Methods of organizing educational activities are divided into several groups:

1. Sources for students to learn: Verbal, instructive, practical methods.

2. According to the direction of the student's thinking: induction, deduction, analogy.

3. Pedagogical impact on the level of management, the level of independence in students' studies according to: the method of educational work performed under the leadership of the teacher. The method of independent years of students. According to the level of students' independent activities: descriptive-illustrative, reproductive, enigmatic presentation method of knowledge, partial search and research method.

According to the sources of knowledge for students: Verbal, instructional practical methods.

1) Verbal methods allow to give as much information as possible in a short period of time, to put riddles in front of students and show them ways to solve them.

These methods create conditions for the development of students' thinking.

A) Explaining: The method of explaining knowledge is that the teacher explains the material, and the students receive it, that is, the knowledge. The description of the educational material should be clear, understandable and short. The explanatory method is used to introduce the theoretical materials of the information system, to give instructions to students on the use of educational tools. It is necessary to explain a number of issues of the primary mathematics course.

For example: when explaining a triangle, the teacher uses triangles of different shapes, colors, and sizes cut from paper. These are triangles, although they are different from each other, but all of them are explained by the fact that they consist of a section, and the angle is taken out of one corner of the triangle.

B) Suhbat: bu eng ko`p tarqalgan va yetakchi o`qitish metodlaridan bulib, darsining har xil bosqichlarida, har xil maqsadlarida qo`llanilishi mumkin, ya'ni yangi materialni bayon etishda,

mustahkamlashda, takrorlashda uyga berilgan topshiriqlarni, mustaqil ishlarni tekshirishda qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Conversation is a question-and-answer method of teaching, in which teachers, based on the students' mastery of knowledge and practical experience, use a system of specially selected questions and the answers to them. leads to the solution of problems and leads to the development of mathematics in a school with a small set.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Thus, it is not a secret that the use of electronic technical tools: projector, electronic board, computers in elementary school mathematics classes with little equipment is one of the requirements for the quality of education today, that is, the use of it in elementary school mathematics classes. Not everyone dares or finds the opportunity to bring it to their classes. No matter what type of educational tools are used in any educational context, if the tool is chosen correctly by the teacher, its effectiveness is always high. Because the listener not only hears, but also sees the reality he is hearing (in whole or in part), observes, thinks, compares and analyzes, draws conclusions. Therefore, if the meaning of life is the existing state of the entire existence, the meaning of education is determined by the different form and content of the tool.

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